

ARTICLE

A Stellar Partnership: National Park Service and NASA partner on 2024 Eclipse Programming through Earth to Sky

Hot Springs National Park (<https://www.nps.gov/hosp/>)

At Hot Springs National Park in Arkansas, the public enjoyed multiple methods for viewing the total eclipse safely and comfortably.
NASA/ Julie Hoover

Helping the public safely experience the awe of the April 8, 2024 total eclipse at National Park Service (NPS) Sites was a team effort! Earth to Sky—an organization that fosters collaboration between NASA and the National Park Service—supporting National Park Service sites in the eclipse path with resources to boost the impact and accessibility of eclipse programming.

Members and partners of the Earth to Sky Partnership with a Hot Springs National Park ranger on Eclipse Day.

Photo Credit: Earth to Sky / NASA

Our Earth to Sky partners, Cris White and Devon Camillieri (pictured second from right and right above), tell the story of this collaborative effort to make this natural phenomenon interesting and accessible to all visitors.

A Once In A Lifetime Experience

Articles by Cris White and Devon Camillieri (Earth to Sky)

The 2024 total solar eclipse provided a unique and powerful experience to connect with celestial movement in space. Eclipse chasers from Hot Springs, the greater Arkansas area, and all over the country had a special opportunity to interact with experts from Hot Springs National Park, NASA, NOAA, and the Earth to Sky Partnership, leaving experts and visitors alike in total awe.

When the Heavens Met the Springs

On April 8th, 2024, almost all of the continental United States witnessed at least a glimpse as the Sun, Moon and Earth came into perfect alignment. Wanting to experience the total solar eclipse in a location immersed in history, nature, and culture, thousands converged on one of only two national parks in the path of totality, Hot Springs National Park.

In the week leading up to this extraordinary event, the Earth to Sky Partnership convened a skillful group of facilitators and experts from NASA's Earth Science Division, NASA's Science Activation, and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA) Space Weather Office to help Hot Springs National Park staff with their ambitious eclipse engagement schedule. This powerhouse team rolled into town ready and excited to engage different members of the community at city events, public and private schools, libraries and parks to prepare visitors for the thrill of the upcoming eclipse.

Families learning to star gaze.

Julie Hoover / NASA

Countdown at Schools, Libraries, Community Events, And More

Members of the team from NASA, NOAA, and NPS visited public and private schools in the area over three days, educating over 3,700 students on NASA and eclipse science and safety. Elementary students found joy in demonstrating an eclipse with stuffed replicas of the Sun, Earth, and Moon, and learned about how solar viewers could keep their eyes safe while viewing the eclipse. The middle and high school students learned about NASA eclipse-focused research from the past and present, how to use their solar viewers, how they could seek out internships at NASA and NPS, and how they could participate in citizen science efforts on the day of an eclipse.

Bridge Street Live programming

Library Programming

Community Outreach

Events Under the Stars

New Eclipse Explorer Junior Rangers taking the Junior Ranger pledge on eclipse day.

Photo credit: Julie Hoover / NASA

Eclipse Festivities: Launching Excitement

In the two days leading up to the total solar eclipse, Hot Springs National Park hosted the Eclipse Fest where the community, eclipse chasers, and scientists could share their excitement. Gathering on the historic Arlington Lawn of the National Park, over 8,600 people learned about NASA Earth Science, space weather, and important eclipse safety lessons, while participating in a plethora of hands-on activities. Children and adults alike were able to create an aurora, build a satellite, view the visible electromagnetic spectrum, use LightSound devices and tactile plates to make observations with their other senses, watch sunspots on the Sun in real time, and create ultraviolet-detecting bead bracelets. Over the two days, attendees marveled at the collaboration between the tables of NOAA, NASA, and NPS experts who came together to build enthusiasm about the eclipse in their community.

On Monday April 8th, the day of the total solar eclipse, Hot Springs National Park came alive with almost 4,000 eclipse chasers and enthusiasts. The National Park Service hosted three official viewing stations across the park, on Hot Springs Mountain, West Mountain, and Arlington Lawn. Each location offered different tabling activities. Spread throughout the park, facilitators helped the visitors view the Sun with solar telescopes and pinhole projectors. They tracked the changes in temperature throughout the event, hosted an accessible solar viewing tent, and made LightSound devices available so visitors could listen to the changing light levels. Some spots even had eclipse quizzes, coloring stations, and an opportunity to record their memory of the coronal activity after the totality had ended. Eclipse Junior Ranger books and activities were extremely popular.

A group using a solar film canopy on eclipse day. This canopy allows visitors to view the eclipse safely without holding up special glasses.
Earth to Sky / NASA

Shining Light on Inclusivity

From the very beginning of planning, the three collaborating agencies made it a priority to plan all eclipse engagement efforts with inclusivity in mind. It was important to ensure that all visitors would feel cared for and comfortable so that they could focus on the celestial experience.

NASA, NOAA, and the National Park Service coordinated to create safe experiences for visitors. At each of the three park locations, there were solar film canopies that were tall enough for people to stand under. Any eclipse chasers using wheelchairs, or who had difficulty holding their solar viewers to their faces, could move under the tent and comfortably look up while protecting their vision. The canopies were wildly popular as many people used the solar film as a great opportunity to get a photo of the eclipse. For future eclipse efforts, the team recommends including signage into this inclusive space to explain its intended use.

At the center of it all, on the busy Arlington Lawn of Hot Springs National Park, the National Park Service set up a low sensory tent. This shaded area provided relief to all visitors, but was particularly useful to families and individuals in need of accommodation.

Throughout the week, the team demonstrated different tools to empower visitors with visual impairments to experience the eclipse. LightSound is a solar eclipse sonification tool created by Harvard University to help Blind and Low Vision communities hear the changing light levels during the eclipse. Each of the three viewing locations throughout the park had one of the devices set up with an external speaker. As the eclipse progressed, it was powerful to hear the way the pitch of sound shifted. Additionally, each site had a set of tactile plates that explained the eclipse using Braille. The plates demonstrated the alignment of the Sun, Moon, and Earth in space during the solar eclipse, different solar features such as prominences, loops and sunspots, the layers of the Sun from core to corona, and recreations of drawings of previous total solar eclipses. These tools enabled everyone to experience the eclipse.

A crowd gathered on West Mountain to watch the eclipse.
Julie Hoover / NASA

"The Earth to Sky partnership would like to thank all their partners, other agencies, volunteers, and Hot Springs National Park for helping to create such a stellar event."

--Cris White and Devon Camillieri, Earth to Sky

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